

LIST OF JOURNALS FOUND IN SMS 2012-2019.

Published studies	Journal name	JCR ^a	SCImago ^b	Q ₂₀₂₀ ^c
3	Empirical Software Engineering	✓	✓	Q1
2	BMC Bioinformatics	✓	✓	Q1
2	Information and Software Technology	✓	✓	Q2
2	Scientific Programming	✓	✓	Q4
1	Bioinformatics	✓	✓	Q1
1	IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering	✓	✓	Q1
1	Environmental Modelling and Software	✓	✓	Q1
1	Computers and Chemical Engineering	✓	✓	Q1
1	IEEE Access	✓	✓	Q1
1	Mathematical Programming	✓	✓	Q1
1	Computer Standards and Interfaces	✓	✓	Q1
1	Future Generation Computer Systems	✓	✓	Q1
1	Journal of the Royal Society Interface	✓	✓	Q2
1	Web Semantics	✓	✓	Q2
1	Journal of Grid Computing	✓	✓	Q2
1	Journal of Heuristics	✓	✓	Q2
1	Data Base for Advances in Information Systems	✓	✓	Q2
1	Journal of Computer Science and Technology	✓	✓	Q3
1	International Journal of Information Technology and Decision Making	✓	✓	Q3
1	Library and Information Science Research	✓	✓	Q3
1	Distributed and Parallel Database	✓	✓	Q4
1	International Journal of Software Engineering and Knowledge Engineering	✓	✓	Q4
1	Journal of Systems and Information Technology	-	✓	-
1	International Journal on Digital Libraries	-	✓	-

^a <https://jcr.incites.thomsonreuters.com>^b <https://www.scimagojr.com>^c 2020 quartile in JCR index.